

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES FOR FOSTERING ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030 projected an inclusive and equitable quality education to all citizens, achieving the right to education for all irrespective of their gender. Women in general and student-mothers in particular are builders of a nation as their male counterparts. In ensuring that student mothers receive an inclusive and equitable quality education, they combine multiple roles with their academics. This study examines the relationship between post-graduate student-mothers' multiple roles and academic success in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and three hypotheses tested at a .05 level of significance. The study adopted a survey design type. Data was collected from a sample of 55 postgraduate student-mothers undergoing their Post Graduate Diplomas at Lagos State University through a self-developed questionnaire. Findings showed that there was no significant relationship between the number of children and role conflict of student mothers $F(2, N = 55) = 2.875, p = .411$. Also, there was no significant difference in the role conflict of student-mothers based on marital status, $F(1, N = 55) = 2.426, p = .119$. However, there was a significant difference between the support student-mothers receive and their academic achievement, $t = -2.416, df = 53, p = .019$. Student-mothers who received support had a better academic performance than their counterparts who did not receive support. It is recommended that among others the government and school management should provide child care and create campus support units.

Keywords: multiple social roles, post-graduate student-mothers, academic assessment, inclusive and equitable quality education.

Abstract: This paper looks at the position of educational management in Nigerian universities in fostering entrepreneurial skills for sustainable development. There is a need for sustainable development in Nigeria, universities are given the role of nurturers of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is very essential for the growth and development of any nation. It provides individuals with self-employment and gives a sense of self-reliance. The promotion of entrepreneurial skills in Nigerian universities would no doubt boost the Nigerian economy. Entrepreneurship education is implemented into the curriculum to provide support for entrepreneurial initiatives, administrators are mentors in empowering students to become creative minds as well as problem solvers. Thus, it is pertinent for Nigerian university administrators to carry out certain roles to achieve this and this paper is geared towards discussing these various roles. The problems encountered by university administrators in their roles for the promotion of entrepreneurial skills in their universities were also discussed including lack of funds, lack of facilities, poor training and

inadequate skills to carry out administrative roles amongst others. In conclusion, entrepreneurial skills are fundamental and vital for a country's development. In the university, the entrepreneurship program needs to be implemented as part of the curriculum and recognized as a future design for employability skills and sustainable development. Several suggestions were put forward which included the role of Nigerian university administrators in curriculum implementation to achieve efficiency in the promotion of entrepreneurial skills.

Keywords: Educational Management, Administrators, Entrepreneurship skills, Sustainable development

Introduction

The study explains the role of educational management in Nigerian universities in fostering entrepreneurial skills for sustainable development. Entrepreneurship education is a necessity in the 21st century. There are different skill sets by which profit can be maximized in the area of entrepreneurship. The level of entrepreneurship in a country determines the growth and development of that country's economy. Galindo-

Martin et al (2021) and Lopez Nunez et al, (2020) agreed with this opinion that entrepreneurship acts as a crucial pillar to achieve economic development independently of the conditions of a country. Evidence abounds in Nigeria that a high rate of graduate unemployment exists, which is not due to a lack of jobs, but rather a lack of employable skills that the labour market requires, as well as a skill gap and mismatch (Oladokun & Gbadegesia, 2017). Meanwhile, Emen, Nwanguma, & Abaroh (2012) revealed that 23 million of Nigeria's 40 million unemployed youths were unemployed due to a lack of employable skills, with the majority being university graduates. The dire state of the Nigerian economy is a glaring indication that the spirit of entrepreneurship should be inculcated in our leaders of tomorrow. While, Akomolafe, Adegun & Adesua, (2016) think that higher education (university education inclusive) is germane to the development of a total person for sustainable development. In another case, the nation's economy is believed to be growing at about 7% annually, paradoxically, it has failed to provide jobs to its citizens, particularly the youths who constitute 43% of the entire population (Oke and Shokunbi, 2013). Furthermore, the problem in Nigeria is not just poor level of school completion rates, but that of skills mismatch (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2014). Most of the graduates either take up jobs that are not related to their fields of study or roam the streets in search of white-collar jobs (Folu, 2013). Evidence abounds in Nigeria that a high rate of graduate unemployment exists, which is not due to a lack of jobs, but rather to a lack of employable skills that the labour market requires, as well as a skill gap and mismatch as seen by (Oladokun & Gbadegesia, 2017). In addition, one of the numerous goals of university education is the goal of improving the abilities of the students to properly adapt to the social, economic and political spheres of the society. This is why 21st-century education hopes to inculcate innovativeness and creativity within the students to foster new ideas that would develop and change the world (Ausat et al, 2023). They further held on to the fact that education is of utmost significance in the enhancement of entrepreneurship as it is a

comprehensive and interconnected system which establishes attitudes and values that are pertinent to entrepreneurship. Again, Ofor-Douglas (2021) rightly put it that for educational managers or administrators to succeed in university educational management, the administrators need some basic skills to succeed such as conceptual skills, human relations skills and professional skills. Where it is properly harnessed and utilized, the administrator is bound to achieve the goals and objectives of the university.

It is against this background that this paper aims to properly outline the distinct roles that educational administrators in Nigerian universities should play to foster entrepreneurial skills for the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria. The objective of this paper is to detect the various ways Nigerian university administrators can utilize their skills in other to effectively play the role of fostering the growth and development of entrepreneurial skills in their universities. A lot of issues have been highlighted by different scholars on how best to foster entrepreneurship skills in undergraduate students in Nigerian Universities, to fill the missing gap the researcher is carrying out this study on the role of educational management in Nigerian universities for fostering entrepreneurial skills.

Education

In the 21st century education is important for the sustainability of any nation; therefore, it is reasonable that the educational sector will be given rapt attention. Education serves as a channel to hone an individual intellectually and equip them with relevant knowledge and skills. An individual whether in a formal or informal setting will be given the right type of training to sustain them in society. The worth of education is measured by the quality of its outputs. Unfortunately, there is diminishing quality of outputs of educational institutions at various levels in Nigeria and many of the outputs of educational institutions are now myopic in academic competency and quality thus implying that all is not well with the system that is producing them (Egbebi, 2016) as cited in Oyelade and Egbebi, (2018). Young (2012) postulated that education does not or should not mould people to a rigid pattern, it should be unique, seeking to draw out and develop the special blend of talents that each person possesses. Accordingly, Abiodun, Ogunkunle, Ganiyu & Adekola (2020), opined that education is the process of nurturing, transmission, and application of such knowledge that transmits the development and sustenance of every society from day to day. Education equips an individual with skills and knowledge that makes them relevant members of society. However, Jansen (2004) as cited in Oyelade and Egbebi (2018) opined that academic achievement is the process of developing the capacity and the potential of individual pupils (students) to prepare them to be successful in a specific society or general towards the improvement of the teaching and learning situation for the benefit of both the teacher and the learners including the larger society. Vista, Kim & Cre (2018) asserted that modern education is migrating to the acquisition of a broader range of skills and getting critical thinkers, but the challenge globally now is how to harness and support students in developing and upskilling broader skills. Evidence abounds in Nigeria that a high rate of graduate unemployment exists,

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University education

At the end of the education programme, individuals are trained to become part of a nation's economy with various employability skills. Universities provide a great number of manpower year in and year out. In the word of Adelakun, et al, (2023) asserted that higher education (university education inclusive) grooms an individual for the sustenance of the nation's economy and overall development of the nation at large. Adamu (2015) thinks that it has to do with the ability of the institution to meet the expectations of the users of manpower about the quality of skill acquired by their outputs. Furthermore, Adamu goes on to say the institution can meet certain criteria relating to academic matters, staff-student ratio, staff mix by rank, staff development, physical facilities, funding and adequate library facilities. The goals of university education are tripartite; from teaching and learning, knowledge generation and information dissemination and community service. The university system is made up of faculties and departments, therefore, there is a need for synergy between informal and formal education in proper management of students to produce skilled manpower for the society and the larger society for the economic development of the nation for the 21st-century development of the nation. The goals of University education remain elusive and seem unachievable as the university products (graduates) in Nigeria often time could not marry knowledge acquired in schools with that of the labour market (Olofintoye, & Prince, 2013).

Management

In university education, management is the process of planning, organizing, coordinating, directing, controlling, and communicating to achieve the goals and objectives of the university efficiently and effectively in a seamless manner. This role covers overseeing various departments, programs, staff, and facilities. The University is dependent on effective management for the smooth day-to-day operation of the university, fostering a conducive learning environment and maintenance of academic standards.

Management can be inferred as the coordination of all resources of an organization through the process of planning, organizing, directing, controlling, budgeting and reporting to attain organizational goals (Chiaha, 2013). Management is the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals, working together in groups, efficiently accomplish selected aims (Ofor-Douglas, 2020). Collaborating, Akube (2014) as cited in Chime (2016) asserted that management is a process where a group of people at the highest level of an organization plan, organize, co-ordinate, communicate, control and direct the actions and activities of others who work in the organization towards the achievement of the organizational objectives. It is equally the process of getting things done through others with the help of some basic activities like planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling (Nath, 2016). Moreover, the internal management of higher education (university education inclusive) is teamwork between the staff and students who interact daily with the status of the institution (Obayuwana, 2021). Wang (2016) claimed that proper human resource management is another important principle of sustainable development.

Also, Yang (2019) supported the argument by opining that basically, the figure depicts that proper decisions on sustainable resource management will bring about sustainable growth for a sustainable society. Accordingly, Ahmed (2022) averted that educational management is the systematic coordination and control of an institution's operations, including planning, organizing, directing, and managing, to effectively and efficiently use people and material resources to achieve the goals of teaching and learning, research and community service. Likewise, Olga (2011) cited in Ossat and Jack (2020) views management as a stream of coordinated activities involving planning, organizing, and directing the activities of an organization to determine and accomplish stated objectives with the use of human and material resources. In addition to that, a manager uses these five core functions, which are part of the educational management process, to accomplish the aims and objectives of the educational institution (Das, 2021).

Also, Caldwell (1992) as cited in (Das) said that managers and leaders of self-managing schools must be able to develop and implement a cyclical process involving seven management functions:

- Goal setting;
- Needs identification;
- Priority-setting;
- Planning;
- Budgeting;
- Implementing; and
- Evaluating

This explains why Sobia, Kamra & Nasir (2012) claimed that workshop training is a planned activity, systematic and results in enhancing the level of skills, knowledge and competency that are necessary to perform work effectively. In the same vein, Narbaev, Marco, & Orazalin (2019) suggested that strong governmental institutions are required to enhance Public Private Partnership performance and investment growth. The researcher is of the view that for universities in Nigeria to achieve effective skills (undergraduate students) in Nigerian universities, there is a need to properly equip them (students) with management skills to enhance their performance in the various endeavours that they find themselves. The role of education as a tool for national development can only be performed through effective management and administration (Wahab et al., 2017).

Educational management

A system of education can be successfully but mindlessly run, especially when stakeholders, educators and learners themselves approach education with the assumption that they are so deeply familiar with the process that it fails to carefully consider the outcome of what is being called education. (Ikegbusi & Admu, 2021). Thus, effective educational management is an instructional technique that integrates the teaching of literacy, skills and job content to move learners more successfully and adequately towards their education and employment, educational management and staff development programs: the main spring for achieving a goal (Egwu, 2022).

Educational management is the accurate application of management ideas in the discipline of education (Bush, 2003) as cited in (Das, 2021). For educational managers or administrators to succeed in university educational management, the administrators need some basic skills to succeed such as conceptual skills, human relations skills and professional skills, where it is properly harnessed and utilized, the administrator is bound to achieve much. Nwaka and Ago (2021) mentioned that educational management is a process that involves the dedication of all aspects of managerial tasks towards achieving the highest standards of education needed by beneficiaries of education, including secondary education, parents, employers, and society at large. Quality management is a different way to organize the efforts of people. (Dike, 2020). Effective management introduces a significant change in the relationship between those who manage and those who do the work (Brinla, et al, 2022). Meanwhile, Ikegbusi et al (2018) maintain that it also helps the top management to make effective managerial decisions leading to better management of resources and believable in the institute.

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In recent times, the educational system is likened to a program for beggars. After graduation, a student would start applying for a job by sending in applications. The employer of labour would then look out for what skills you have/ how much you can offer to the organization to turn around for increased productivity in the 21st century. To get ahead, students should be made to think differently to create values or be value creators, problem solvers and generate productivity as this is what employers are looking for. In line with the situation the following should be done:

For the fact that employers are looking out for employees who are productive; ☐ Students should learn trades and develop them to unlock their potential.

☐ Students should discover their purposes and develop them. ☐ Society needs to improve on their value content.

People need to expand on their thinking. Over 90% of what we are learning will soon become useless after graduation in society especially since artificial intelligence is gradually taking the place of humans in this 21st century, so universities need proper management of the skills of their users which are their customers and the larger society. **Sustainable Development**

Sustainable development encompasses the notion of meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This explains why Ekwueme,

Ekon, Ezenwa & Nebife (2016) think that education in sustainable development allows every human being to acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes and values necessary to shape a sustainable future. In Nigerian universities, the act of promoting sustainable development involves incorporating principles of prosperity, economic development, social equity and environmental sanitation. Similarly, Emeka-Nwobia (2015) asserted that sustainable development could probably be otherwise called “equitable” and balanced. Entrepreneurship education is crucial for the advancement of sustainable development by giving individuals the proper knowledge, skills and career-oriented mindset which are essential in creating innovative solutions for challenges that may arise economically, socially and environment-wise. In the same vein, Osei-Kojo (2014) cited in Okafor and Egenti (2021) rightly put sustainable development as a development path along which maximization does not lead to a decline in the well-being of the future generation. The university can be a haven for fostering entrepreneurship education which fosters creativity, resourcefulness and network opportunities amongst individuals. Moreover, Akintoye and Opeyemi (2014) claimed that continued sustainable development is only possible or assured when it is agreed upon and indeed concrete steps are taken to raise the level of literacy and numeracy in any society. Furthermore, Juliana and Susann (2017) concluded that sustainable development means an ongoing process with systemic approaches that require creativity.

An entrepreneur is essentially a service provider to a group of people or members of society. These trained individuals will eventually be empowered to launch business ventures which develop a positive atmosphere in the environment contributing to job creation, and economic stability. Nwana (2011) cited in Okofar and Egenti clearly describes an entrepreneur as a person who has goods and services that the community needs and who has the emotional and psychological drive to be a master of these goods and services as well as the means of making them available to the members of the community to which it belongs. Entrepreneurship education would aid students in diversifying their skill set thereby giving them a variation of job opportunities to choose from. However, the absence of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian university curricula is a big setback to this dream as the avenue for learning these skills has not been made available in most Nigerian Universities. Where there is poor entrepreneurship education in a university, students would not be able to grasp the concept of selfemployment and independence. Thus, a student who is not self-sufficient, dependent, and unemployed would resort to theft and other devious means to make quick money. This would further endanger Nigerian society and to a decline in the growth and development of a nation (Ofor-Douglas, 2020) as cited in (Ofor-Douglas, 2023). Although entrepreneurship has been introduced in the Nigerian university curriculum there is still a long way to go as the Nigerian economy is a huge setback in ensuring youth employment, independence and growth and development of a nation. Hess (1987) cited in Nzegbulum and Odionye (2016) thinks that available textbooks devoted too little coverage for entrepreneurship education and some of these books have not been reviewed for many years despite changes in knowledge and technology. This goes to show that little or no attention has been given to the promotion of entrepreneurship education in the university.

Furthermore, the essence of entrepreneurship education is aimed at creating opportunities which not only contribute to economic development but also personal and professional development of an individual. (European Commission 2006) cited in Nzegbulum and Odionye (2016). An individual tends to undergo growth and development when having a sense of independence which can be seen in the form of entrepreneurship. In the same vein, Wu and Wu (2017) asserted that entrepreneurship education should aim at cultivating students' entrepreneurial ability and thinking and promote successful entrepreneurship. Also, Emerson and Obunadike (2008) cited in Nzegbulum and Odionye (2016) perceived entrepreneurship education as that which deals with the attitude and skills that are necessary for the individual to respond to his environment in the process of conserving, starting and managing a business enterprise. Entrepreneurship education is very necessary to equip an individual with what is necessary to be independent in establishing a business. Nwagbara (2012) also cited in Nzegbulum and Odionye (2016) thinks that at the turn of this century, it became obvious that for Nigeria to keep pace with the rest of the world, entrepreneurial education must be placed on the front burner. It goes to show for any nation or economy to thrive entrepreneurship education should be a part of its university's curriculum. It is an essential component of training that not only helps students to assimilate theory and practice but also exposes students to unfamiliar technology, workplace expectations, work schedules and organizational structure (Kiplaget, Khamasi & Karie, 2016). Albania (2014) asserted that close collaboration between the formal and informal workplace should be a must, thus, this would allow exposure to entrepreneurship in practice. Ene-bong (2006) claimed that building entrepreneurial culture in students can be done through "experience". This implies that for students to be trained in entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial education has to start from the basis, that is from nursery, primary, secondary to university level so that they will be well grounded in experience to turn out as well-equipped graduates full of wealth of skilled, knowledge and ideas to the society.

Entrepreneurship Skills

Entrepreneurship is basically when an idea is concocted by an individual usually for a new service to be introduced into the market. Entrepreneurial skills are skills which include management, business acumen, problem-solving, and creativity. For any organization to thrive these skills are vital for growth and development. Ahmed (2022) averred that educational management is the systematic coordination and control of an institution's operations, including planning, organizing, directing, and managing, to effectively and efficiently use people and material resources to achieve the goals of teaching and learning, research and community service. Developing entrepreneurship skills has been identified as a means of providing employment, shunning violence and a powerful weapon for combating poverty in the country. Emphasis on technical and vocational education in the polytechnics and universities of science and technology is highly desired for positive transformation of higher education (university education inclusive) in Nigeria for achieving technological advancement, which is one of the goals of Nigeria's development target (Abiodun Ogunkunle, Ganiyu & Adekola, 2020). They also produced an article that aimed to shed light on

research opportunities for psychologists by exposing gaps in the entrepreneurship literature and explaining how these gaps could be filled. An essential element of education's function in cultivating entrepreneurial spirit involves equipping students with pertinent entrepreneurial competencies. The entrepreneurial spirit refers to the capacity of individuals to recognize and seize opportunities, undertake calculated risks, and transform ideas into significant innovations that benefit society.

Hisrich et al, (2005) also conducted a study to analyze the relationship between the level of entrepreneurship and economic growth in the long run. The attainment of this objective can be facilitated through the implementation of entrepreneurship initiatives inside educational settings such as schools, universities, and other academic institutions. To achieve the objective of entrepreneurship education the program must be highly equipped to help students learn to utilize resources (Oluwade, Suleman & Olumoyegum, 2022). **Furthermore**, it is believed that the entrepreneurship activities that students undertake during college will encourage them to be future entrepreneurs. Individual attributes include orientation, intention, and motivation of students to become entrepreneurs, to create job opportunities for themselves and others and to add value to their businesses (Bosma, et al, 2020). It should aim to alleviate poverty within the existing environmental and economic resources based on the society. (Kumar, Raizada & Biswas, 2014; Scopelliti et al, 2018). Furthermore, Bosma et al, (2020) opined that entrepreneurial activities carried out by students are confirmed to result from simultaneous interaction between social values and individual attributes. Odewale et al (2019) think that the previous research has confirmed that many things can improve the entrepreneurial skills of students, including entrepreneurship education, support from external practitioners such as existing entrepreneurs and a college environment that can have a positive influence on student entrepreneurial activities, although not significant. The problem in Nigeria is not just poor levels of school completion rates, but that of skills mismatch (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2014). A study carried out previously has indicated that many things can improve the entrepreneurial skills of students, including entrepreneurship education, support from external practitioners such as existing entrepreneurs, and college environment that can have a positive influence on student entrepreneurial activities, although not significant (Odewale, et al, 2019). Previous work carried out confirmed that entrepreneurial activity is positively correlated with economic growth (Galindo-Martin, et al, 2019).

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is significant in the role it plays in innovation, sustainable development and economic growth. It educates individuals on knowledge, skills and mindset which equips them to create value and identify and solve problems. Notably, Evans-Obinna (2014) deposited that entrepreneurship education as the process through which individuals acquire a broad set of competencies that can produce greater social and economic benefits to the individuals. Meanwhile, Enu (2012) emphasized that entrepreneurship education is a form of education that seeks to provide knowledge, skills, attitude and motivation to students for entrepreneurial success in any facet of human endeavours. The Nigerian

curriculum accommodates entrepreneurship education as it is a vital component that prepares individuals for real-life dynamics and global competitiveness. Entrepreneurship education focuses on developing real-world skills that will help students lead exceptional lives in a rapidly changing world (Marlborough, 2021). **Also**, Ngerem & Ezikpe (2016) showed that entrepreneurship education is a viable medium for steering the wheels of economic development for university school graduates in Nigeria. Brush (2014) and Kuratko (2005) rightly stated that entrepreneurship education within a school generally consists of a nested set of activities, including curriculum, co-curricular activities, and research efforts. Adeola and Bolarinwa (2010) asserted that entrepreneurship education is any formalized teaching, or training that intends to educate anyone interested in business innovation or small business development. As defined by Uzo-Onkonkwo (2013) entrepreneurship education is any formalized teaching, or training that intends to educate anyone interested in business innovation or small business development.

Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Universities

Presently in Nigerian universities, entrepreneurship education is gaining a foothold with various implementation intensities across universities. A wide range of topics such as business planning, financial management, marketing and venture creation. There are several challenges such as limited resources and, an outdated curriculum which serve as obstacles in this program moving forward. The country's universities were not prepared for entrepreneurship education when they were compelled to commence it. It is not clear whether any special fund has been made available to the universities for the prosecution of entrepreneurship education. The state's conventional facilities for conventional education are being used in the universities. The same personnel for conventional courses are being used for teaching entrepreneurial studies in our universities Nwekeaku (2013). In the same spirit, Adebisi and Oni, (2012) suggested that the absence of entrepreneurship expertise is no doubt the cause of the unemployment problem in Nigeria. An individual has the mindset that upon graduation they will seek white-collar jobs upon completion of school and when this is not possible they remain unemployed still actively sourcing for jobs and rejecting the idea of self-employment. There is an urgent need to reposition education in Nigeria especially the tertiary education (university education inclusive) policies and teaching tools to meet the present reality of entrepreneurship in the 21st century (Olusanya, 2020).

Roles of University Administrators in Facilitating Entrepreneurship Education

Administrators play a crucial role in bringing about entrepreneurship education and encouraging an entrepreneurial system in Nigerian universities. Resource allocation, strategic leadership and partnerships within

the industry will give the ultimate entrepreneurship educational experience. Furthermore, administrators serve as intercessors for policy implementation, curriculum reform and promotion of entrepreneurship principles in teaching. Interdisciplinary collaboration, student-associated entrepreneurship clubs and competitions, mentorship programs and funding opportunities. These and more can be promoted by administrators who will foster risktaking, and business-oriented mindset, innovation, and perusal of

different entrepreneurial endeavors that are influential in sustainable development and economic prosperity. Graduates in universities must not only maintain and develop Knowledge and skills that are specific to their discipline or occupation but also possess generic skills, dispositions and attributes that are transferrable to many occupational situations and areas (Boateng, Eghan, & Adu, 2015).

Problems of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

There have been myriads of administrative problems confronting the educational system in Nigeria such as decayed facilities and infrastructures, poor funding, poor quality products, low morale of teachers, incessant crisis and inadequate research, but the system does not seem to be able or willing to provide a solution for solving this problem (Ekwealor and Orizu, 2021). The following are issues that are of concern to the researcher:

- 1. Poor facilities for teaching and learning:** A known problem that some Nigerian universities tend to face is insufficiency in infrastructure that is grave to quality teaching and learning which encompasses poor facilities for teaching and learning. Facilities such as libraries, laboratories, and classrooms are needed for effective teaching and learning. The absence of this leads to limitations on the part of lecturers and students alike in teaching and learning. Generally speaking, there is a complete or devastating absence of relevant teaching and learning facilities in Nigerian universities. Ugwoke, Basoke et al, (2013) divided it into the absence of relevant textbooks and the poor state of infrastructure.
- 2. Absence of relevant textbooks:** In saying there is an absence of relevant textbooks, this means that there is no appropriate text for a particular course. In university education textbooks are important to build upon learning, knowledge and preparation for exams. The absence of relevant textbooks makes room for limitations in knowledge acquisition. Idibie (2004) as cited in Amadi and Amakodi (2019) mentioned that teaching and learning without textbooks would mean a lot of memorization as well as make the words of the teacher final authority. This does not pave the way for competency in entrepreneurship.
- 3. Poor state of infrastructure:** A poor state of infrastructure does not necessarily mean the unavailability of facilities but a poor maintenance culture and a dilapidated state of infrastructure. Obeleagu-Nzelibe and Moruku (2010) also cited in Amadi and Amakodi (2019) said that the state of infrastructure in the Nigerian university system is, to say the least, embarrassing. Infrastructures such as electricity, water, conducive classrooms, functional entrepreneurship centres and telecommunications networks are in bad shape. In a learning environment where facilities are not readily available. The university will not be conducive enough to learn. Salihu, Andu, Ibrahim, & Mohammed (2020) further stated that in Nigeria there are limited established entrepreneurship education centres to develop and coordinate entrepreneurship at different ministries, organizations and educational institutions. In the few areas centres are established, these centres are not adequately equipped). Taba (2012) rightly states that school resources are scarce and, in most cases, insufficient because enough funds may not be made available for the acquisition of such resources. John (2018) concluded that infrastructure facilities and equipment in our universities are not in good condition and the majority are even outdated.

4. Unqualified Teachers/ Lecturers: The impact of teachers cannot be underrated; a teacher/lecturer will always play an essential role in nurturing students and in the case of unqualified teachers there will be interruption in the academic performance of students. Salihu, Audu, Ibrahim & Mohammed (2020) established that most entrepreneurship education teachers lack the methodology for teaching entrepreneurial skills and entrepreneurship. It is only trained teaching personnel that can understand and impart entrepreneurial subject matter in an inspiring manner to develop entrepreneurial-minded students who will meet the nation's economic growth. Universities struggle not only to recruit qualified individuals with experience but also find it difficult to retain them.

5. Poor Funding: Poor funding is a deficiency of funds to carry out and maintain operations in a particular organization. These problems have become a recurring demand in the history of Nigerian education, there has been declining budgetary allocation to education and yet an increase in enrolment. The effect of this on education management is better imagined. The system lacks the necessary funds and materials to implement the various programmes and policies. The situation has become worse due to the current financial crisis which has impacted the country's economy (Ekwealor & Orizu, 2021). The shortfalls in each school's annual budgetary allocation are frustrating efforts at meeting the salary obligation of teaching and non-teaching staff, resulting in three to seven months of arrears in salary payment (Ahmed, 2017). On the other hand, Chinelo (2011) cited in Emeka-Nwobia (2015) rightly stated that it is no longer news that poor funding and poor control of financial resources which are intricately tied together have destroyed many laudable programmes and policies of Nigeria's National Policy on Education. Salihu, Audu, Ibrahim, & Mohammed (2020) asserted that there is a need for substantial funds for teaching in practical terms entrepreneurial education for financing startups and expansion of business ventures to produce successful entrepreneurs. **Conclusion**

Entrepreneurial skills are fundamental and vital for a country's development. In the university, the entrepreneurship program needs to be implemented as part of the curriculum and recognized as a future design for employability skills and sustainable development. It can be said a country which is high on entrepreneurship can produce independent individuals which will curb the problem of unemployment and crime rate in the country. Entrepreneurial skills should therefore be encouraged. Entrepreneurship education which can be used to hone entrepreneurial skills is vital in growth, development and economic growth. It is very important that individuals especially youths can be empowered.

Suggestions

The following were suggestions made for the study:

1. Training programs and workshops should be established to spread the word about entrepreneurship.
2. Facilities and relevant materials should be provided for entrepreneurship education.
3. Entrepreneurship education should not only be learned but should be able to impact positively in the sense that on completion of the relevant degree, individuals alike are equipped with employability skills.

4. Funds should be made available either by the government or private individuals.
5. National University Commission (N.U.C) and the various universities in Nigeria should pay top priority to entrepreneurship skills to be inculcated into the students to be useful to themselves, society and the globe at large.

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